

Challenges in Translating Cultural Expressions from Chinese Language to English Language

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Abstract: Chinese is thought to be one of the hardest languages for second language learners to learn. Many foreign businesses have been drawn to China by globalization, but others have been discouraged by the language barrier. Chinese translators are employed by both foreign and Chinese businesses to translate from Chinese to English or vice versa to get around language barriers. There are still a lot of unresolved problems in the field of translation, especially those connected to the concept of cultural equivalence in all its forms. Such writings will arm translators with the knowledge they need to steer clear of problems and complications. This investigation seeks to close that gap. The results of the study showed that most, if not all, cultural expressions are challenging to represent or understand for these fundamental reasons. However, the results of this study will encourage researchers in other academic fields to investigate this topic in several linguistic disciplines.

Keywords: Chinese learners; Linguistics; Translation; Expressions

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1. Introduction

1.1 Topic Background

The Chinese language is believed to be one most challenging language any second language learner would ever learn. While globalization has lured many foreign firms to China, others have been held back due to language barrier. To overcome the obstacles related to language, both foreign and Chinese firms in and outside engage the services of Chinese translators, either to translate from Chinese to English or vice versa. But even experienced translators still encounter challenges in the translation of Chinese language. This is mainly as a result of some Chinese words, phrases, and expressions have both superficial literary meaning and functional meaning with culture linen also known as "文化内涵." When a Chinese-English translator encounters this and still gives the literary meaning where functional meaning is needed, in some cases, the translator ends up giving a "Chinglish" translation of the expression. This will lead to committing translation error, or in some cases, a sacrilegious offense, if a Chinese translation is repeated word for word without regard for cultural context, the message may come off as disrespectful or just untrue to its original content. For a skilled Chinese translation to provide outstanding results, comprehension of both cultures and linguistic details are crucial. Therefore, assessing a language's cultural sensitivity can significantly improve translation quality.

Translation's goal is to facilitate communication. Humans must use language as their primary form of communication, and whether consciously or subconsciously, people's culture and values have an impact on their use of language. Thus, translation is concerned with both language and culture; nonetheless, most translation interpretations do not specifically refer to cultural manifestations. According to Catford, "translation is the replacement of literary content in one language by equivalent textual material in another language" (1965). Like this, Savory (1968) asserted that the mental equivalency that lies behind all of translation's linguistic representations is what makes it possible. Even Newmark (1981), who placed a high priority on cultural factors in his process and procedure suggestions, left out culture from his description. He defined translation as "the art of trying to replace a written message and statement in one language with a similar message or statement in another language."

Nida (1964) considered cultural factors while attempting to explain translation and the duty of a translator, claiming that "the role of a translator is to assist the conversion of the message, context, and cultural characteristics from one language into another and generate an analogous reaction to the recipients." Furthermore, he emphasized that the message from the original language contains cultural meaning. Newmark (1988) defined concepts from other cultures as include ecological, material, and social cultures. Expressions relating to social institutions, politics, religion, sculpture, gestures, and behaviors are also featured. There are cultural expressions in proverbs, collocations, phrasal verbs, and figures of speech like metaphors. When the translator is from a completely different culture than the author, cultural phrases employed in social, religious, geographical, political, literary, and media texts can be a substantial source of difficulties in translation.

1.2 Topic Significance

Few research has been done on the functional translation of cultural expressions into Chinese. Most of the research that are currently accessible have largely focused on one or more basic language structures, such as idioms, proverbs, and collocations; however, this study will combine all of them. To address what seems to be a gap in the translation literature, this research was conducted. This article will help students in translation departments by providing solutions when they meet cultural phrases utilized in this study.

1.3 Problem Statement

There are still many undiscovered issues in the subject of translation, particularly those pertaining to the idea of cultural equivalency in all its manifestations (types) (Al-Mubarak et al., 2014). For instance, although many idioms, proverbs, and other phrases with cultural connotations should be translated functionally, some translators choose to interpret something using semantic translation (literal translation). This may be explained by the translator's overall ignorance of both languages and the significance of functional equivalence. As a result, the translator might not accurately transmit the message's intended meaning and might instead misinterpret it. Studies examining and identifying the actual difficulties that translators have while translating from Chinese to English—as well as the factors that contribute to these difficulties—are few. However, such literature will prepare translators in advance to avoid such issues and complications. This study aims to bridge that gap.

1.4 Research Objective

The following is the study's main goal:

1. Describe the special difficulties that graduate and undergraduate English translation students at Taiyuan University of Technology have when converting certain cultural phrases from Chinese into English.
2. Identify the factors behind the difficulties they have when translating cultural expressions.

1.5 Research Prompt

These research inquiries are addressed in this paper:

1. What difficulties do graduate and undergraduate students at Taiyuan University of Technology have when translating idioms and proverbs from the Chinese language into English?
2. What are the reasons behind those difficulties?

2. Literature Review

Additionally, it helps to reduce cultural and geographic barriers (Bahaa-eddin 2011). According to some experts, including Khammyseh & Karak (2015), translation is the transfer of ideas from one language to another. This procedure must express all the meaning prosperities of the source language to appear in the destination language (SL). A professional translator "must bear in mind that he is conveying thoughts and messages, not simply words," according to Shunnaq (2012).

Additionally, translation may be described as an effort to make articles produced in the source (SL) and target (TL) languages equivalent (Panou 2013). Thus, obtaining complete equality in interlingual translation is a challenging objective. According to Belloc, there aren't any identical analogues (1959). Because of this, translators employ equivalence to create the most accurate approximate or equivalent between the texts in the source and destination languages (TLT). As a result, there is a possibility that the translations will either over-translate or under-translate, which might result in the loss of meaning or the addition of unnecessary meaning.

The concept of equivalency has not yet been fully defined, despite several attempts to pinpoint its dimensions, such as "semantic VS. Communicative," "formal VS. Functional," and "Cognitive VS. Affective." It is crucial to remember that while certain linguists and translation experts were able to define the translation process quite precisely with regard to the idea of equivalency, they were unable to differentiate between "meaning" and "message," which means that the transference of the human verbal translation cannot be entirely performed. This study focuses on functional equivalence (FE), which deals with typical cultural lexical elements and occasionally calls for the creation of brand-new particular words. Because of this, the (FE) phrase often neutralizes or generalizes the (SL) word while occasionally adding a particular meaning (Sholihin 2018).

The challenges students have while comprehending collocations was another topic covered by Bani-younes (2015). To pinpoint these issues, a questionnaire was distributed to 40 MA English language majors. According to the results, participants encountered a range of cultural and sociolinguistic challenges, such as word order within a single collocation, linguistic difficulties with religious expressions, and a lack of suitable counterparts in the target language. The statistics also indicated that the people lacked sufficient collocation abilities. Finally, Yousefi (2017) focused on analyzing translation quality, particularly when it comes to religious texts. The purpose of the study was to determine if the quality of Islamic books translated by Muslims was superior to those translated by non-Muslims by using Waddington's model for evaluating translation quality. The results show that there is no correlation between translators' religious beliefs and the caliber of their translations.

3. Research Methodology

The methodology provides a summary of the data collection and analysis process. This part addresses problems such as the research design, the study population, the number of samples to be drawn from the population and how they will be drawn, the procedures and equipment to be used to collect data from respondents, and ultimately, how the data obtained will be evaluated and analyzed.

3.1 Research Design

The research design demonstrates the logical flow from the study's opening research questions to its findings.

Figure 1: Research Design (Source: Researcher's construct)

3.2 Study Sample

A sample of 45 first-year master's students from Translating department in the Taiyuan University of Technology was randomly selected based on availability. The students will have to satisfy any of the following requirements to be eligible. The students will initially be translation majors who have completed all the advanced translation courses and are acquainted with translating various kinds of documents. Specifically, translation of culture-specific texts. Secondly, the students would have formerly engaged or currently engaged in translation-related jobs either as intern, part-time, or full-time workers. The sample was selected on the grounds of convenience. Additionally, experts that teach translation at the Taiyuan University of Technology will also be interviewed.

3.3 Data Collection

The instrument used in this study was a translation test in a questionnaire format which was explicitly designed for the current study's needs. The questionnaire was divided into two parts, demographic information of the respondents and the text to be translated, which is the test. The demographic part included information such as the respondent's age, gender, education level, job experience duration and type, advanced translation examination, and other exam qualifications.

The test, which consisted of 10 sentences, was piloted, and pretested before being given to the chosen group. According to Newmark's classification of cultural words, the statements included cultural expressions. Many proverbs, idioms, collocations, and metaphors were considered culturally specific expressions, so they will be considered. These expressions were taken from the poem 《书房》 by 梁实秋, and the translated version which was used to compare the respondent's response was taken from 第六章 散文的翻译.

The test was undertaken through the use of the popular Chinese questionnaire APP called 问卷星, as it is a popular type of questionnaire common to Chinese students and also very suitable for this study. The questionnaire was distributed with an introduction letter that outlined the study's intent, with an assurance to the respondents that their response will be anonymous and will be used for this present study.

3.4 Test Validity and Reliability

University academics with expertise in teaching linguistics and translation were consulted to guarantee the test's face and content validity. They were requested to offer insightful comments, notes, and ideas regarding the acceptability of the content. The test's reliability was evaluated using test-retest procedures. Ten master's degree candidates who

matched the overall population's demographics took the test. To provide them access to other resources, it was assigned as homework. After two weeks, the same pupils took the exam once more.

4. Results and Analysis

The section provides explanations of how the data and test results obtained from the respondents were analyzed and then displayed with the use of a pie chart, tables, and other necessary graphics. 4.1% Survey Response Rate Between June 24 and July 1, 2021, a period of seven days was used to conduct the questionnaire. A total of 28 completed questionnaires were returned after 45 respondents completed the survey. Only 25 of the 28 questionnaires submitted were deemed genuine since they were all entirely filled out, the respondents had all had professional translation experience, and they had all passed certain translation exams. The other three surveys were not fully completed. Consequently, 25 questionnaires were chosen for the examination of text translation and descriptive statistics.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The results from the descriptive statistics show that the 24 (96%) of the respondents were females while only 1 (4%) of the respondent was male. This shows a certain imbalance among the respondents.

Figure 2: Gender

The age of the respondents shows that the greater percentage(80%) of the respondents are between the age range of 20-25, while a smaller percentage of 20% is between the age range of 26-30.

Figure 3: Age

From the diagram below, all the respondents had a job experience, but their job experience duration differs. Fourteen of the respondents had less than a year of job experience, while 9 of the respondents had between 1-3 years, and one respondent each had 3-5 years and five years and above working experience.

Job Experience Duration

Figure 4: Job experience duration

For the job experience type, 10 (40%) respondents worked as interns, while 13 (52%) respondents had a part-time job experience, and just only 2 (8%) of the respondents had full-time working experience.

Job Experience Type

Figure 5: Job experience type

As shown in the table below, 68% of respondents have completed an advanced translation course, while 80% have completed other translation-related courses, such as Advanced Literary Translation and English Chinese Comparison and Translation. Once more, 92% of the respondents are knowledgeable with translating various materials, particularly those that are culturally distinctive.

Table 1: Description statistics

Question	Options	Frequency	Percent
Have you passed any advanced translation courses?	Yes	17	68%
	No	8	32%
Total		25	100%
Have you passed any other translation courses?	Yes	20	80%
	No	5	20%
Total		25	100%
Do you have experience translating various text kinds, particularly writings that are distinctive to a certain culture?	Yes	23	92%
	No	2	8%
Total		25	100%

4.3 Semantic Analysis of The Translated Text

To this study, five culture-specific expressions found were used in the discussion of the analysis. The table (1) below provides the original Chinese expression, which is taken from the poem called 《书房》 by 梁实秋, and also its translation as found in 第六章 散文的翻译. The discussions for each of the expressions are found below the table. The respondent's translations and the original translations were compared to identify the translation strategy employed.

Table 2: Original Text translation

Original version of 《书房》	散文 translation
周彝商鼎	The wine vessels of Zhou, the cooking vessels of Shang
铸成钱币	Copper when it is cast into coins
布帛刀错	Cotton and silks, knife-shaped money
毛边连史	Rough edges and uncut pages of ancient volumes
桂馥兰薰	Lofty flowers like bay trees or fragrant thoroughwort

1. 周彝商鼎: was translated only by 15 respondents out of 25 respondents. All the respondents opted for literal translation as they translated the statement as Zhou Yi's tripod. According to the Oxford dictionary, a tripod is "a stool, table, or cauldron resting on three legs" or "a three-legged stand for supporting a camera or other apparatus." None of these definitions depicts what the poem was portraying. This definition sees 周彝 as a name while 商鼎 as an object/thing, but according to the translation adopted in this study, 周 and 商 are two different names, while the objects (wine and cooking vessels) are 彝 and 鼎. It is obvious they didn't misunderstand the meaning of the phrase and interpreted it in a different way. Some respondents who didn't translate just opted for the pinyin of the phrase and wrote it as "Zhou Yi's Shang ding."
2. 铸成钱币 was translated as "they were made into coins" by eight respondents. Compared to the translation used in this study, the respondents omitted to mention copper, and against "casting" they opted for "made," which is inappropriate because coppers can only be made into money through the process of casting. The rest of the respondents who translated it as "when it is cast into coins" didn't mention "copper" (铸).
3. 布帛刀错 was translated as "the wrong cloth and silk knives" by seven respondents. This is an obvious "word-for-word" translation by these respondents. It is obvious that the respondents expected although the term should be functionally translated to communicate the desired meaning, that the literal or dictionary meaning would be acceptable. This same problem applies to 5 respondents who translated it as "the cloth knives." This is not just a direct translation but also a wrong translation. The respondents omitted translating the meaning

of 帛 and 错, thereby leading to a partial omission of translation. The rest of the respondents omitted translating the phrase entirely. The original translation used in this study was translated as “cotton and silks, knife-shaped money,” which is more detailed in the functional translation.

4. 毛边连史 was translated as “the rough edge of the history” by 14 respondents, and this translation is unclear when compared to the translation used in this study, which was translated as “rough edges and uncut pages of ancient volumes.” This translation is more detailed compared to the above respondent's translation. Another 11 respondents rather translated it as “printed with rough edges,” which is even more incomplete as it never mentioned history or ancient times. This is a pure omitted translation.
5. 桂馥兰薰 was translated as “Osmanthus fragrans” by 20 respondents. “Osmanthus fragrans” in Chinese is called 桂花, and 桂花 is a species of flower mostly found in eastern Asia which have a uniquely sweet and buttery fragrance and mostly used as tea by the Chinese. The respondents generalized the two different flowers (桂 and 兰) mentioned in the phrase to mean only 桂花, omitting 兰, which meant fragrant thoroughwort. The translation used in this study translated the phrase as “lofty flowers like bay trees or fragrant thoroughwort,” but the reason for translating 桂馥 by the author as “lofty flowers,” as lofty itself means superior or elevated. The researcher believes that the more suitable translation of 桂馥 would have “the fragrance of Osmanthus fragrans.” The rest of the respondents didn't give any translation of the phrase and just wrote the pinyin of the phrase, probably because it was difficult for them to comprehend and they weren't able to grasp the intended.

The study's findings demonstrated that most, if not all, cultural expressions are difficult to represent or grasp for these basic reasons. For starters, these statements are culturally diverse in terms of language structure, semantic denotation, and socio-cognitive significance. Again, most respondents lack a complete comprehension of cultural expressions, making identification, recognition, and translation into the target language problematic. The significance of these sentences was lost on the responders.

5. Conclusion

The study's findings demonstrated that for these fundamental reasons, most, if not all, cultural expressions are difficult to represent or grasp. To begin with, these phrases are culturally diverse in terms of language structure, semantic denotation, and socio-cognitive significance. Again, most respondents lack a complete comprehension of cultural expressions, making identification, recognition, and translation into the target language problematic. The significance of these sentences was lost on the responders. Educate translators on culturally specific words. The conclusions of this study, however, cannot be extended beyond the selected participants due to the small sample size. However, the findings of this study will stimulate other academics to perform research on this issue in several linguistic disciplines.

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